

Applications of Refractive Index in Chemical Constitution. Part IV. The Constants K_r and R_T in Straight Line Mixture Law Compared with Other Constants R_L and R_G

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The new constants K_T and R_T have been applied in thirteen binary mixtures in cyclohexane and the results compared with the Lorentz-Lorenz function R_L and the Gladstone-Dale function R_G . Both the constants K_r and R_T offer better agreement than R_L and R_G .

The new constants^{1,2}:

$$K_r \left(= \frac{M}{n^2 + 2} \text{ for } n_D^{20} \right) \text{ and } R_T \left(= \frac{Mn}{d} \ln T_b \text{ for } n_D^{20} \text{ and } d_4^{20} \right)$$

have been applied for some binary mixtures with a view to comparing the values with the Lorentz-Lorenz function³:

$$R_L \left(= \frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2} \cdot \frac{M}{d} \right)$$

and the Gladstone and Dale function⁴:

$$R_G \left(= \frac{n - 1}{d} \cdot M \right).$$

Thirteen binary mixtures were studied and in all of them one of the component was cyclohexane. The mean value of the constants from at least three mixtures of each set has been obtained. The calculated values for R_L were obtained from the atom, group, and structural values obtained by Vogel and co-workers⁵; except in the case of the phenolic OH group, the R_L and R_T values were calculated from data from other sources⁶. The calculated values for K_r and R_T have been obtained from values recorded in previous communications^{1,2}; except for K_r , the OH (phenolic) is obtained from the value of phenol and comes out to 4.26. For the constant R_G , the calculated values are not given. The results are recorded in Tables IA and IB.

In the majority of the binary mixtures, the deviations from observed and calculated values with the mean value from mixture (in case of liquid—liquid mixtures from 1 to 9) or with the calculated value shown in the table (in case of solid-liquid mixtures from 10 to 13) are least for K_r and less for R_T compared with the other two functions, R_L and R_G . The solvent (cyclohexane) selected is non-polar, but some of the other constituents having different substituents are polar. It is seen that polarity induces an influence and the phenolic and nitro groups as substituents produce greater deviations than the chloro or bromo substituents do.

1. This *Journal*, 1962, 39, 57; 1963, 40, 550, 553.

2. *Ibid.*, 1962, 39, 135.

3. *Phil. Trans.*, 1858, 148, 887.

4. *Ann. Phys.*, 1880, 11, 70; 1880, 9, 641.

5. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1833.

6. Heilbron and Bunbury, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", Vol I, 1953.

TABLE IA

K_r, R_r, R_L, and R_G values from mixtures in cyclohexane.

	<i>K_r</i>	<i>R_r</i>	<i>R_L</i>	<i>R_G</i>	<i>K_r</i>	<i>R_r</i>	<i>R_L</i>	<i>R_G</i>
		1. Benzene.				5. Dimethylaniline.		
Mean value from mixture	18.39	146.2	25.79	44.12	27.64	227.1	42.97	72.71
Obs. value	18.35	147.4	26.19	44.54	27.52	229.5	41.02	71.12
Calc. value	18.09	147.3	26.39	..	27.40	227.9	40.91	..
		2. Chlorobenzene.				6. <i>o</i> -Cresol.		
Mean value from mixture	26.01	175.1	29.94	53.86	24.93	184.4	33.06	57.45
Obs. value	25.98	175.6	31.18	53.47	24.64	185.2	32.59	56.20
Calc. value	25.07	176.0	30.17	..	24.72	185.3	32.80	..
		3. Bromobenzene.				7. <i>m</i> -Cresol.		
Mean value from mixture	35.98	189.3	35.74	59.63	24.83	184.8	33.34	57.08
Obs. value	36.23	187.3	34.74	58.84	24.73	185.1	32.78	56.45
Calc. value	34.47	187.4	33.07	..	24.72	185.3	32.80	..
		4. Nitrobenzene.				8. <i>o</i> -Chlorophenol.		
Mean value from mixture	28.05	182.4	34.26	58.26	29.36	193.4	33.37	57.36
Obs. value	27.90	185.2	32.73	56.90	28.99	184.5	33.21	57.54
Calc. value	26.96	185.1	31.04	..	29.33	182.4	32.99	..

TABLE IB

	<i>K_r</i>	<i>R_r</i>	<i>R_L</i>	<i>R_G</i>
		9. <i>m</i> -Chlorophenol.		
Mean value from mixture	29.47	*182.90	33.03	57.01
Obs. value	29.03	185.40	33.42	57.84
Calc. value	29.33	182.38	32.99	..
		10. <i>p</i> -Dichlorobenzene.		
Mean value from mixture	35.07	201.2	36.14	61.13
Calc. value	34.97	202.8	36.02	..
		11. <i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene.		
Mean value from mixture	53.02	224.6	42.78	87.85
Calc. value	52.65	225.7	42.84	..
		12. <i>o</i> -Nitrophenol.		
Mean value from mixture	32.31	191.1	34.01	60.73
Calc. value	31.23	214.8	36.69	..
		13. <i>p</i> -Nitrotoluene.		
Mean value from mixture	32.23	216.9	38.10	66.06
Calc. value	31.29	189.4	33.59	..

*These values from mixture were inconsistent.

EXPERIMENTAL

Among the chemicals used, cyclohexane (b. p. 81.0°) was B. D. H. spectroscopic chemical and benzene (b. p. 80.0°), B. D. H. AnalaR reagent. Chlorobenzene (b. p. 132.0°), bromobenzene (b. p. 155.5°), nitrobenzene (b. p. 210.0°), dimethylaniline (b. p. 193.0°), *o*-cresol (b. p. 191.0°), and *o*-chlorophenol (b. p. 175.5°) were B. D. H. laboratory pure chemicals and were twice distilled in Pyrex apparatus and the middle portions were stored in Jena or Pyrex stoppered bottles. *m*-Cresol (b. p. 210.5°) and *m*-chlorophenol (b. p. 214.0°) were Riedel laboratory pure chemicals of which the middle portions of the distillates were stored for use in a like manner. The solid *p*-dibromobenzene (m. p. 86.8°), *p*-dichlorobenzene (m. p. 53.0°), *p*-nitrotoluene (m. p. 54.5°), and *o*-nitrophenol (m. p. 44.9°) were all B. D. H. laboratory pure chemicals. These were purified first by crystallising from ethanol and then by sublimation. The products so obtained were stored for subsequent use. Standard qualitative tests of the chemicals were done before purification. The pressure in each set was practically constant and ranged between 74.0 and 74.3 cm. Experimental procedures adopted for measuring boiling point, density, and refractive index were the same as mentioned in the previous communication².

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